

Title: Using Social Media To Determine Outcomes That Matter Most To Patients

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Abstract

Background: Social media discussions around medication use by clinicians and patients have created a public record that can provide new, timely insights into various unique and existing topics, including adverse events. Unstructured patient discussions from social media platforms and online forums could offer many patient narratives that traditional qualitative research efforts may not typically capture. The current research focuses on analyzing social media data to understand outcomes that matter most to patients.

Objectives: Firstly, to assess the value and feasibility of using social media to understand the patient perspective on medical product risks and living with different medical conditions. Secondly, to determine and propose the best methods for distilling insights from social media.

Methods: A third-party vendor acquired 12 months of publicly available posts from Twitter® and patient forums mentioning a chemotherapy medication for breast cancer (BC). Data were automatically processed to standardize drug names, vernacular symptoms and to remove duplicates as well as “noise.” Posts were manually reviewed by analysts to confirm automated outputs and to apply sentiment tags. We then used Binary Matrix Factorization (BMF), Bayesian Estimation (BE), Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), and Regular Expression Filtering (REF) to identify trends and associations between user sentiment and topics such as adverse events (AEs), quality of life, and experiences living with BC.

Results: Analyses of social media posts indicated that diverse and high-volume discussions of the patient journey and perspective towards a wide range of topics are held in online forums. A total of 16,015 posts were collected and processed; 1,389 were then manually reviewed. Issues about insurance, infection, employment, the emotional impact of treatment or disease, and side effects were most commonly discussed. BC patient’s most frequently discussed chemotherapy side effects were alopecia and peripheral neuropathy. The various methods implemented were mixed: LDA did not provide unique insights, but BMF helped ascertain patient preferences among the different topics discussed. Sentiment tags provided a valuable dimension in analysis methods; however, these may need to be applied at the product level to reflect complex patient perspectives best. Twitter provided a large volume of less

specific statements, while forums encouraged patients to provide rich narratives similar in detail to in-person interviews.

Conclusions: Social media is an important tool in understanding the patient journey. However, not all social media sources are appropriate for information gathering. Obtaining meaningful insights computationally is challenging, and automated methods can facilitate human analysis. Findings using this process would presumably result in detailed stories from patients, similar to focus groups or in-person interviews with patient groups while reducing the time and costs associated with qualitative research management and coordination. Continued work in this area would require a comprehensive taxonomy to help identify a wide variety of topics and a dedicated sentiment classifier for each product or therapeutic area of interest. Much work remains to determine best practices for using this rapidly evolving data source.

Key Points

- Online discussions can provide insight into the patient experience that might not be captured by traditional qualitative research efforts, providing a cost-effective alternative to focus groups.
- Our analysis of 16,000+ social media posts pertaining to chemotherapy treatment for breast cancer revealed a wide range of topics from the patient perspective, including the impact of disease progression and tolerability of treatment side effects.
- Binary Matrix Factorization and sentiment tagging were useful tools in ascertaining patient preferences among the different discussion topics. A hybrid automated-manual process is necessary to reduce human effort while also ensuring that the patient experience is adequately conveyed.
- Future work in this area would benefit from a comprehensive taxonomy for patient experience topics and a dedicated sentiment classifier for specific products or therapeutic areas of interest.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, patients and clinicians increasingly have taken to social media to discuss negative and positive experiences of medication use, creating a public record that has the potential to provide new, timely insights into a variety of new and existing topics, especially adverse events [1]. Several online communities have evolved into full discussion forums for exchanging health and medicine-related information. At the same time, recent advances in information technology have enabled research teams in both the private and public sectors to overcome previous challenges posed by data volume and unstructured text by using tools like natural language processing and machine learning [1-6], prompting stakeholders from industry, regulatory, and academic groups to explore whether there is value in using social media platforms for pharmacovigilance activities [2].

Social media tools (e.g., medical community blogs, crowdsourcing, social media pages) may include information on patient's perspectives regarding symptoms and impacts of a disease or condition [7]. Targeted social media searches may be helpful during the preliminary stages of a study to complement literature review findings, inform the

development of research tools (e.g., qualitative study discussion guides), or as a supplement to traditional research approaches (e.g., literature, one-on-one interviews, focus groups, or expert opinion) [7]. The FDA Patient-Focused Drug Development (PFDD) guidance further discussed the value of SML in incorporating the patient voice into qualitative and quantitative research [7, 8]

Conversations on social media can provide unprecedented insights into the patient experience. This can precede post-market surveillance as it holds value across the drug development lifecycle (Fig 1), extending from assessing patient's priorities and unmet needs to supporting the development of novel outcome measures and conducting a benefit-risk assessment using safety insights. Most importantly, these insights come straight from the patient in their most authentic voice. The anonymity provided by social media further enables patients to be more forthcoming and honest with their experiences, from details around treatments and drugs to any concerns or fears around the same. This can allow regulators, prescribers, and Pharma industry sponsors to map out the patient journey in the patient's terms with the improved diversity, volume, efficiency offered by social media data sources.

Figure 1: Social media can be a valuable source of information throughout the product life cycle

Previous issues encountered when leveraging social media to generate patient-centric insights are related to data volume and an inability to parse through unstructured text. However, researchers can mitigate these challenges with natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML) tools. There are limitations to social media listening from a social and ethical perspective as well. The legitimacy of social media data can be questioned regarding indication and experience; however, the volume of data available and tools to process and clean data sources may negate the issue and minimize noise. Beyond this, there have been long-held ethical concerns around using people's data for commercial purposes. Therefore, patient consent, appropriate forums, and other such discussions will be critical when deriving social media strategy, with engagement with legal/compliance pertinent throughout the process.

Although social media tools can provide valuable data, researchers should consider the limitations related to sampling. Most social media sources have no mechanism for verifying the patient's identity or clinical and demographic characteristics. Additionally, different demographic groups tend to use different types of social media. It is essential to use various social media tools to gather information from the demographic group(s) being targeted based on this variability.

With growing interest in utilizing social media from Pharma and other healthcare stakeholders, the value of social media as a pharmacovigilance data source is being explored. Powell *et al.* (2016) examined the use of Twitter®, Facebook®, Reddit®, and patient forum data as a tool for augmenting traditional safety data across their product portfolio [4]. A recent Cardiac Safety Research Consortium (CSRC) think tank focused on using social media for cardiac safety monitoring. The consortium recognized that while social media should never replace other drug safety sources, it can learn about patient preferences. Furthermore, published studies evaluating the use of social media to support pharmacovigilance activities have observed that patient conversations often extend beyond discussing medication side effects. For example, a pilot study funded by Abbvie found that while social media did not contribute to new safety signals, it provided perspectives into the patient's perspective, including medication adherence, tolerability, and quality of life [5]. Such insights may be helpful in drug development phases that precede post-market surveillance – for example, study design or development of patient-reported outcomes for clinical endpoints. Most methods for capturing this type of information (e.g., patient-reported outcomes and patient experience) typically rely on a semi-structured interview format. A patient may be asked a series of standardized questions, limiting the scope of patients' responses [9, 10].

In contrast, unstructured discussions acquired from social media platforms and online forums could provide a vast range of patient narratives that may not be typically captured by qualitative research effort; however, given the nuance and length of such discussions, automated techniques would be necessary to reduce manual effort. To our knowledge, no framework involving automated processes exists for this specific purpose (uncovering insights beyond adverse events for qualitative analysis).

This paper assessed the value and feasibility of social listening, including data gathering from social media, in understanding outcomes that matter most to patients and to determine and propose the best methods and processes for distilling the insights from social media.

2. Methods

2.1. Data Acquisition

We used a combination of automated and manual processes to acquire, classify and analyze English-language posts published on Twitter® and patient forums between July 2016 and July 2017 mentioning a chemotherapy medication (Chemo) for BC treatment. Twitter® posts were accessed via Gnip, Twitter's data vendor subsidiary, using the PowerTrack product for query submission and response. Patient forum posts (i.e., digital message boards or online

communities that contain conversations dedicated to specific therapeutic areas or health concerns) were accessed via SocialGist, a third-party vendor of social media data.

2.2. Automated Data Classification

Post Type Classification: The majority of social media posts published daily did not pertain to experiences with medical products. Social media can produce substantial “noise,” i.e., a higher potential for false positives or negatives without proper filtering. Researchers can implement automated methods for filtering and classifying social media data to assist with sifting through high volumes of data to prioritize only relevant discussions. Filtering uses different techniques to classify each post and extract drug names and descriptions of medical concepts from social media text.

For this analysis, a Naïve Bayes classifier was used in a preliminary filtering step to remove posts containing bot- or spam-like language ("spam"). Using the same conceptual process as spam filters for email, we developed the classifier with a machine-learning algorithm and a human-labeled training set of more than 300,000 posts to recognize those with valid user descriptions of product mentions and medical concepts ("meaningful mentions") [4, 6]. Aside from identifying literal duplicates using verbatim matches, a rule-based approach was applied to consider “fuzzy” matches as duplicates, using increased computation power (based on a Bloom filter), as described in Powell [4] and Freifeld [6]. Next, the data was de-duplicated using text-based similarity scores and source-specific characteristics (such as the phrase "RT" used in Twitter to denote a "retweet"). We preserved the text and metadata of the original post by consolidating duplicated posts into a single version. We then sequestered redundant copies of each duplicate post from the primary data set and subsequent processing and analyses.

Keyword Tagging: To extract keywords of interest from the posts, we applied an NLP algorithm that identifies references to products and medical concepts, as described elsewhere [6]. The processor implements a tokenizer and a tree-based dictionary algorithm to parse the post length and match strings of the input text to terms from pre-established taxonomies. These taxonomies were developed to map vernacular language to defined concepts about medical products and health outcomes [6].

Drug product: To identify product mentions in each post, we used a product taxonomy that maps vernacular language to standardized product names. By having the active ingredient with all products, we could analyze data at the substance level. In addition, there are a handful of generic entries that served as a catch-all for non-specified products. For example, if a user mentioned that they are taking a steroid but does not mention the substance or brand, the *steroid mention* is automatically tagged to an *unknown drug*. At the time of this report, the product dictionary contains 5,130 synonyms mapping to 1,050 drugs, devices, and vaccines.

Medical concepts: To capture medical concepts related to disease and medication experiences as described by patients, we used an existing symptom dictionary that maps vernacular language to formal MedDRA® (Medical

Dictionary for Regulatory Activities Version 19) preferred terms [11]. At the time of the analysis, the symptom dictionary contained 11,554 synonyms, mapping to 2,200 MedDRA® preferred terms. An example of this mapping is displayed in Table 1, with the standard MedDRA term in the first column and vernacular synonyms included in the second column.

Table 1: Example of MedDRA term and vernacular synonyms

MedDRA preferred term	Synonyms
Rhinorrhoea	runny nose, congested, congestion, nose runny, nose running, nose runnin, snotty nose, snot, sniffly, sniffles, running nose, my nose run, nose run, stuffy

2.3. Curation

Following automated processing, posts with automatically-identified descriptions of medical concepts underwent additional manual review. This “human” curation step focused on removing false positives, refining the taxonomies, and assigning product-symptom attribution, where applicable.

During the human curation step, analysts also confirmed any descriptions of potential clinical adverse events, according to whether a patient described a health system interaction (HSI). For example: *"...I only completed 10 of the 18 weekly dose chemo treatments. I stopped early due to sudden onset of severe neuropathy that my oncologist said would get worse and could be permanent ..."*. This step helped identify posts that mentioned medically-confirmed adverse reactions, hospitalizations, emergency room admissions due to adverse reactions, discussions with a healthcare provider about concerns related to the medical product, or intentions to discuss a medical product experience with a healthcare provider. As such, we used the HSI concept to denote adverse events or medical product experiences that patients consider severe, troublesome, or even intolerable.

Posts were also manually classified as containing positive, negative, neutral, or mixed sentiment. Positive posts might have included phrases indicating thankfulness or comments on benefit, while negative posts might have contained strong language expressing anxiety, concern, sadness, or anger. We differentiated neutral and mixed-sentiment posts in these analyses to distinguish posts that expressed balanced but opposing sentiments from those that expressed no sentiment at all. Table 2 provides examples of each sentiment class.

Table 2: Examples of positive, negative, neutral, and mixed sentiment posts

Sentiment Classification	Example Post
Positive	“I love chemo for making my quality of life better, worth the headaches.”
Negative	“ Chemo is truly not worth the side effects.”
Neutral	“No one will admit chemo is what’s caused my feet past 1.5yr 24HR day neuropathy.”
Mixed Sentiment	“Was wondering why pain’s up to an 8. Right. chemo day. I love what it does for me, but injection day’s a bit rough.”

2.4. Analytical Methods

We explored a range of statistical methods for both pattern recognition and hypothesis testing. Methods included Binary Matrix Factorization (BMF), Bayesian Estimation (BE), Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), and simple string searches to filter the data using regular expressions. For these analyses, we presented only the results of curated data as the benefit of ensuring noise reduction outweighed the drawbacks of using a small sample size. All analysis methods described below were conducted using customized Python scripts.

We implemented BMF to compress keywords for products and medical concepts into basis vectors to reveal patterns [12]. Each vector is then reviewed to identify patterns in sentiment-keyword associations, leveraging both the sentiment tags and keywords from the processing and curation steps.

Bayesian estimation was then used to determine statistically credible differences between distinct data groups – here, products and outcomes (side effect, sentiment, quality of life theme) – as a method for identifying outcomes that matter to patients. BE is a method for group difference analysis that includes modeling of uncertainty [13]. This approach provides credible intervals for possible differences in means, differences in standard deviation, and effect size, where a credible interval is a range of values within which an unobserved parameter value falls with a particular, subjective probability. We used the results from the basis vectors identified in BMF to inform the group difference test on select symptoms that appeared in the basis vectors and the top frequency count tables. In cases where an outcome occurred in both positive and negative sentiment BMF basis vectors, we used BE quantitative metrics to help clarify the possible effect of the symptom on sentiment. The narrowest form of a credible interval is the Highest Posterior Density (HPD) interval. For the analyses, the set of posterior distributions over the latent parameters and their differences are plotted with the 95% HPD intervals and reference values.

Next, we used LDA to identify latent topics in the data [14, 15]. LDA is a three-level generative Bayesian hierarchical model of a corpus of documents. The document and topic distributions are assumed to be drawn from a

Dirichlet prior distribution [14, 15]. First, we modeled each document as a multinomial distribution over topics and then modeled each as a multinomial distribution over words. LDA can be viewed as data compression where raw text documents are summarized and labeled by their most probable topics. Topics can then be summarized by their most probable words.

Finally, to identify posts discussing quality of life, we applied filters to the curated data using groups of regular expressions. These groups consisted of keywords related to certain attitudes or daily activities frequently noted during the curation step. We compiled vernacular synonyms and phrases about each group into a proof-of-concept "User Experience Taxonomy" used to query the data. The purpose of this exercise was to provide a basis for future taxonomy work and serve as a proxy for automated natural language processors dedicated to outcomes that matter most to patients. Ideally, this proof-of-concept would be expanded upon in the future and leveraged in a more sophisticated method using NLP.

3. Results

3.1 Data Collection and Classification

A total of 16,015 posts about a chemotherapy product for BC patients were collected from Twitter and patient forums (Figure 3). Of these, 28% (n= 4,443) were removed during the initial automated processing step due to similarity to spam posts. Of the remaining posts, 12% were automatically identified as posts containing descriptions of medication side effects and were manually reviewed by curators, where sentiment tags were applied to true positives and false positives. Of these, 41% expressed neutral sentiment, 28% expressed negative sentiment, and 27% expressed positive sentiment (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Data collection and classification

The most commonly discussed topics among BC patients were alopecia and peripheral neuropathy (Figure 3). Figure 4 shows the most commonly discussed posts that mentioned some health system interactions (HSI), including medically-confirmed reactions, suggestions from nurses for side effect mitigation, and changes in dose regimen to reduce symptoms. The most commonly discussed topic in these posts was peripheral neuropathy (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Most commonly discussed topics on Twitter and Forums amongst BC patients

Figure 4: Most commonly reported concepts with HSI posts on Twitter and Forums amongst BC patients (excluding *Nonspecific reaction* and *Unevaluable event*)

3.2 Analysis Methods

Using the results from the BMF analysis above, we ran several group difference tests using BE to determine statistically credible differences between several distinct data groups, specifically, to identify which common side effects concerned patients the most. To determine this, we evaluated whether there were statistically credible differences between the sentiment of posts mentioning specific common side effects and the sentiment of posts mentioning other side effects for each product of interest.

Statistical credibility of a difference can be inferred by looking at the difference of means plot. For example, if there is a " $2.9\% < 0 < 97.1\%$ " label on the plot, that means that the probability of mean 1 being greater than mean 2 is 97.1%. If the 95% HPD interval does not contain 0, then there is a statistically credible difference. If it contains zero, then there is no statistically credible difference.

For BC, we looked at groups of posts describing peripheral neuropathy, alopecia, and pain (including both general references to "pain" and specific references to localized pain in extremities), madarosis, and nail disorders. The data show with statistical credibility that the average sentiment in posts mentioning peripheral neuropathy as a side effect is more negative than the average sentiment in posts mentioning other side effects (Figure 5). Evidence also suggests that the average sentiment in posts mentioning alopecia as a side effect is more positive than posts that mention other side effects (Figure 6). However, when comparing posts mentioning *hair loss on the head*, specifically, and those mentioning eyelashes and eyebrow loss, user sentiment was significantly lower among mentions of eyelash and eyebrow loss.

The average sentiment in posts mentioning general pain as a side effect, or localized pain in extremities, is more negative than in posts that mention other side effects (Figure 7). No statistically credible difference was observed in sentiment associated with posts mentioning madarosis or nail disorders. Additionally, we examined posts that mentioned pre-medications for chemotherapy and supportive treatments (e.g., Benadryl, Claritin, Zofran, dexamethasone) compared to those that did not and found that sentiment is more positive among the posts mentioning pre-medications.

Figure 5: Difference of means and 95% HPD for posts mentioning peripheral neuropathy compared with posts that mention other side effects

Figure 6: Difference of means and 95% HPD for posts mentioning Alopecia compared with posts that mention other side effects

Figure 7: Difference of means and 95% HPD for posts mentioning pain and pain in extremity compared with posts that mention other side effects

Our sample taxonomy for quality of life aspects and patient perceptions comprised 285 colloquial phrases describing eight categories: infection/immunity, treatment interruption, employment, mobility, emotional impact, HCP distrust, treatment duration, and insurance. The user experience topic with the most mentions was "Emotional impact," consisting of references to depression, anxiety, despair, and stress (Table 3). About 46.1% of the posts referenced emotional impact, and 37.4% referenced infection/immunity; many of these discussions referenced the high cost of the treatment in scenarios where users did not have health insurance coverage.

Table 3: User experience topic volumes

MedDRA® Preferred Term	COUNT (%)
Emotional impact	46.05
Infection/immunity	37.41
Insurance	11.77
Employment	2.53
HCP distrust	0.89
Mobility	0.75
Treatment duration	0.30
Treatment interruption	0.30

4. Discussion

This paper has described several methods for incorporating social media data into patient risk characterization initiatives. We implemented a combination of automated and manual processes to filter and analyze patient posts from Twitter and online forums about outcomes that matter most to BC patients exposed to chemotherapy medication. This section reflects on the methodology we chose and summarizes the type of insights these methods can provide.

Results from the various methods implemented were mixed. The LDA analysis did not yield notable results for the product or patient population; specifically, the language in posts with varying degrees of positive and negative sentiment did not differ meaningfully. Among the more valuable techniques was combining BMF with BE methods to identify research areas to target. BMF revealed basis vectors associated with positive and negative sentiment in discussions regarding the chemotherapy and quality of life events. At the same time, BE allowed us to quantify the significance of the association between the sentiment, product, and event. This combination of methods may be useful for hypothesis generation, suggesting different theories to test in future project phases, or eliminating topic areas when resources are limited.

Easy to automate statistical methods were used for this study. Bayesian estimation does not require as much human input as t-tests. In the absence of specifically justified priors, the prior distributions used can be extensive and vague to express great prior uncertainty in the values of the parameters. This causes the prior to have minimal influence on the posterior estimates of the parameters and allows a modest amount of data to overwhelm the prior assumptions.

While unsupervised learning methods such as LDA and BMF used for pattern recognition do have hyperparameters, heuristics exist for hyperparameter selection in all of these methods. As with most unsupervised learning methods, however, human curation is still needed in the interpretation phase of the analysis. In addition, given the nuance of social media data, incorporating a human-in-the-loop approach would be preferable regardless of the automated methodology chosen.

All statistical analysis methods used in this study leveraged existing machine learning and natural language processing capabilities, enabling us to filter and analyze the data downstream quickly. Since these tools were initially developed to support pharmacovigilance purposes [4, 6], much of the resulting data pertain to descriptions of perceived drug side effects and how treatment side effects impacted patients. That said, these topics are important to patients, as evidenced by the large volume of online conversations where patients seek advice on side effects and how to mitigate them. While using this existing technology has provided an expedient starting point for identifying

the potential of using social media for patient risk characterization, developing additional, dedicated classifiers for future work in this area would be preferable.

Grasping social media insights into the patient experience is challenging to do computationally for multiple reasons. First, since social media language – mainly that used by well-informed patient populations – can be complex and problematic for natural language processors: patients may describe the medical history, disease symptoms, side effects in one sentence, posing a challenge to automated interpretation; sarcasm can be difficult for robots to detect. Second, due to the multifaceted nature of these discussions, it can be difficult to standardize and transform unstructured text from online conversations into aggregate data for analysis while still retaining much of the significance or nuance of these narratives.

Given these reasons and that we used unsupervised learning methods for pattern recognition, some degree of human interpretation is necessary to make the most out of the data; however, reviewing all raw posts manually is unrealistic and time-consuming. Therefore, it is essential to understand what types of expressions can be easily standardized and detected automatically to create data points that will reduce manual curation, facilitate downstream analysis, and create a richer picture at the aggregate level. For example, hospitalization could be used to denote severity and automatically determined by using phrases like "visit to the emergency room."

Furthermore, there are several limitations to using the dictionary approach described in this report. First, the dictionary must be populated and maintained by curators, who must use judgment when choosing the synonym patterns. Specifically, as we do not yet have a framework for assessing sensitivity and specificity for a given individual pattern, we lack a quantitative methodology for determining whether to include a pattern or not. Secondly, the approach is fully rule-based, thus unable to take advantage of statistical models of context, in terms of syntax or semantics, to determine whether a given pattern applies.

We also found that being able to incorporate sentiment into the analysis added depth to the patient posts. As mentioned previously, each post was tagged for sentiment manually to avoid noise resulting from using a generalized classifier. While manual annotation was manageable for the scale of this evaluation, we recommend automated classification for future work where datasets may be much more significant. In addition, we assigned at the post level only, rather than at the phrase or sentence level, which may have produced more representative results and reflected the complexity of patient perspectives. For posts with more than one expression of sentiment, while it is possible to address posts with multiple sentiments by using a "mixed sentiment" tag, this may not be as useful or straightforward in downstream analysis. It may be better to apply the sentiment to specific products, medical concepts, or experiences and implement therapeutic-specific or even product-specific sentiment classifiers

Given the complex nature of discussions regarding the products of interest, it was determined that using an existing automated sentiment classifier would result in noisy data. Complicating factors of the data include lengthy narratives

from forums expressing multiple types of sentiments towards various topics and patients describing multiple products within single posts. Therefore, we chose to assign sentiment manually to best capture the sentiments conveyed in particularly nuanced language. While manual curation of sentiment was manageable for the scale of this analysis, we recommend using automated sentiment classification for future work where datasets may be much larger. Another limiting factor is that our process involved assigning sentiment tags at the post level only, resulting in a single sentiment tag per post, even where a patient expressed different sentiments towards many other things in a single post. While we chose to resolve this challenge by using the "mixed" sentiment tag, the ability to apply multiple sentiment tags to specific products, medical concepts, or experiences would result in richer insights. In addition, when automating sentiment classification for this type of data, we recommend using therapeutic-specific or even product-specific classifiers.

While many medical concepts and adverse events were discussed among the BC patient population, clear trends were more or less impactful than others. High-level themes included knowing what to expect regarding treatment progress, disease evolution, and side effect impact, emphasizing certainty and uncertainty. Discussions about infections and immune system suppression were common, covering a wide range of contexts. The focus was often on the ability to socialize and work despite increased infections while undergoing treatment [*"All coughs and sneezes make me paranoid these days. I want to save up any immunity I have to keep going strong at my job for (a) school district"*].

Patients' views towards treatment were significantly impacted by their reported prior experiences with similar medications, similar symptoms, or other patients' anecdotes about their own experiences.

For example, we observed that patient perspective on the chemotherapy was often described relative to prior experience with Adriamycin and Cyclophosphamide (A/C treatment). Patients who described negative experiences with A/C expressed fear when starting chemotherapy. Patients who did not have difficulty with A/C were hopeful that their experiences with chemotherapy would be similar. However, even patients who had expected to experience a particular side effect still felt blindsided by the severity and persistence of that side effect. For instance, many chemotherapy patients mentioned that they anticipated experiencing neuropathy, and some were dismayed when the side effect appeared to be lasting long after treatment had concluded. Therefore, patient-gearred materials may be an opportunity to cover a more comprehensive overview of what patients expect when they start (and stop) treatment. It may also be positively impacted by HCPs providing better information on what to expect. So a benefit of this analysis, and others in the future, is that it may detect areas where we should focus information and education programs.

In addition, patients who experienced a particular symptom due to their medical conditions may not be as bothered by a similar side effect caused by a medication. For instance, we noted more positive sentiment associated with posts that mentioned taking pre-medication alongside chemotherapy treatments (e.g., dexamethasone) or before supportive medicines (e.g., antihistamines with Neulasta) to mitigate side effects – an additional degree of

preparation or readiness for a side effect. This may be worth examining further to understand other factors that might drive patient tolerance or their perception of treatments and diseases. While the positive sentiment associated with these posts may result from the fact that by using pre-medications, the patients are genuinely experiencing fewer or milder side effects (or at least that patients believe these treatments to be effective), it may also suggest the degree to which patients are concerned about experiencing specific side effects. A patient might take additional measures to reduce the severity of a side effect that they might find less tolerable than other possible side effects.

Lastly, many patients repeatedly expressed gratitude that the forums existed as a place where they could learn from each other, perhaps suggesting a need for additional resources designed and written by patients for patients -- specifically those who may be treatment-naive, newly diagnosed, or just starting new treatments [*"The lack of info and support has completely boggled me. I am grateful that there are these message boards"*].

5. Conclusion

Our research suggests that social media represents potentially valuable untapped data sources in understanding the patient perspective on medical product risks and patient's general concerns while living with different medical conditions; however, not all social media sources are appropriate for digital listening. Twitter can provide higher-volume, less detailed information, while forums can provide rich narratives in similar detail to in-person interviews.

We have found that obtaining detailed and meaningful insights into the patient experience is challenging to do computationally. However, automated methods can help to filter out data that might be more relevant and pertain to different themes. Also, sentiment information can provide an additional dimension that facilitates automated analyses and manual reviews. Therefore, we recommend that such digital listening strategies involve a processing pipeline that includes preliminary spam filtering to reduce highly irrelevant data, natural language processing informed by product-specific or therapeutic-area taxonomies combined with automated sentiment classification. Once processed, analysts should interrogate these data with questions via BE and BMF to better understand the magnitude of particular topics of interest, followed by reviewing sample narratives describing each topic.

Using a hybrid automated manual process as we have done here can increase analyst's likelihood of focusing on valuable data while truly honoring the patient voice. Findings using this process would presumably result in detailed stories from patients, in detail similar to focus group or in-person interviews with patient groups, while reducing the time and cost of focus group management and coordination. Limitations of social media include reliance on patient self-identification and diagnosis, which can be inaccurate. Challenges still exist with diversity and capture rates as different demographic groups tend to use different types of social media.

Declarations

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Conflict of interest: George Quartey and Sergio Ley-Acosta are employees of Genentech Inc. during the study. Andre Nguyen is an employee of Booz Allen Hamilton, Inc., an Information Technology Company responsible for conducting the research. Carrie Pierce was an employee of Booz Allen Hamilton, Inc. during the study.

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